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CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

D11.1 Development of the project Dissemination and Communication plan

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
DSS	Decision Support System
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
IPEB	Intellectual property and Exploitation Board
IPL	Intellectual property log
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IWT	Inland waterway transport
KPI	Key performance indicator
Plan	Communication and Dissemination plan
PC	Project Coordinator
NST	Standard goods classification for transport statistics
SM	Social Media
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

The main goal of the Dissemination and Communication Plan is to raise awareness of the project activities and results in order to make CRISTAL a successful project. This deliverable aims to present the dissemination and communication strategy and plan as well as the associated actions that will be implemented during the CRISTAL project. The strategy is integrated under WP11 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation.

The leader of WP11 (EUMO) will be responsible for the overall management and support of the activities defined under the present dissemination and communication plan and will develop the main tools and materials to be used during the project.

All partners will also be actively involved in the dissemination and communication actions implementation and are highly committed to ensure a satisfactory dissemination of the project's results.

In general, the expected contribution from partners is to:

- Implement publicity and dissemination campaign in their own countries and at European level.
- Exploit their contacts and their networks.
- Participate in relevant events to promote the project and its outcomes.
- Supply news and updates for the CRISTAL web portal, Social Media channels and newsletter.
- Help to keep the project's Social Media Channels (SM) alive and active.
- Contribute with the scientific papers mentioning the CRISTAL project.

C&D activities are ongoing or “working” activities thorough the whole duration of the project and even beyond. The impact and purpose are to give all the targeted audience the possibility to be notified about the latest research and development within the CRISTAL project, therefore the plan will be constantly updated, as well as content of the project communication channels.

In this C&D plan we will also consider the liaison with partners existing networks, twinning project and initiatives to identify synergies and opportunities for collaboration (see chapter 2.14).

1.1. Introduction

The CRISTAL project's ambition is to increase the availability and thus the attractiveness of the inland waterway transport mode by a minimum of 20% and to demonstrate on its three pilot sites (Italy, Poland and France) strategies to improve reliability by 80%.

CRISTAL project will develop IWT capacity at 50% even during extreme weather events. Towards that CRISTAL will co-create, test and implement integrated, cooperative and innovative solutions in its three pilot partners' areas identified in Italy, France and Poland.

The project considers the aspects of technological innovation/development and digitalization. Further advancement towards the Physical Internet, governance solution and business models, will be proposed while targeting sustainability and infrastructure resilience requirements.

The global C&D objective is to prepare and encourage the use and wide acceptance of the project outputs. This will be achieved through internal and external communication measures, dissemination activities and coordinated exploitation of results and innovations. The objective of the exploitation of the project results and wider project dissemination is to present the solutions proposed by the project and to maximize the commercialisation of results in a post-project phase.

In WP4 (lead: UAntwerpen) the generic living lab approach will be “activated” and the mechanisms of the stakeholder's involvement will be a part of a Dissemination Plan that will present a strategy to engage and communicate with stakeholders. A plan will be created, for each phase, specifying stakeholders that will be interacted and how. For each stakeholder, the objective will be explained in terms of communications, key messages, actions to be put in place (brainstorm sessions, questionnaires, workshops, etc.) and channels.

Work Package WP11 of the CRISTAL project focuses on:

- To continuously plan, monitor and provide means for the CRISTAL partners to share their knowledge within the consortium and to integrate research activities as well as to exploit the developments and/or communicate and disseminate the results to the scientific and industrial community and to a wider audience.
- To develop a multi-layered communication and dissemination (C&D) plan and define strategy and steps to outline key messages and target audiences.
- To define project visual identity (logotype, colour scheme, brand guidelines, project template.).
- To define and develop project website and Social Media channels to reach an audience.
- To propose several KPI's to access the level of visibility and stakeholders.
- To comply with open access of publications generated from the project.
- To prepare a segmentation of stakeholders (port managers, inland transport managers, scientific community) and IWT operators (ALICE).
- To identify, qualify and protect the results generated by the consortium (ALICE).
- To coordinate the IPR issues (UNEW) with partners and generate the IPEB (Intellectual property and Exploitation Board).
- Creating IP log (CERTH) detailing existing background IP and any IP developed during the project.

WP11 will achieve this thanks to the work of 3 tasks, led by EUMO, where different partners will contribute (see Table 1 below).

D11.1 Communication and Dissemination plan is the first deliverable of WP11 and aims to maximize the impact synergetic and measurable actions of Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation that will encompass:

- Report the dissemination and communication plan that defines the strategy and specific steps to identify the target audiences and communication actions,
- Outlining the Stakeholders, target audiences and key messages of the project,
- Design and develop a project website, social media channels,
- Targeting audiences with key messages
- Plan dissemination outreach actions and dedicated means/channels for each stakeholder group
- Develop the templates and visual identity of the project (Brand guidelines, logo, templates, typography, colour schemes),
- Proposing a several KPI's to access the level of visibility and efficiency of the C&D actions,

- Making use of results in the project pilots and facilitating the use of results in further European waterways,
- Making results available for use by others.

This will ensure that any valuable knowledge generated in the project is identified and not only made accessible to potential end-users but is also transferred to them.

1.2. Mapping CRISTAL project outputs

Purpose of this section is to map CRISTAL's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1 Alignment of D11.1 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
<i>D11.1 Project Dissemination and Communication Plan</i>	Reports the dissemination and communication plan developed that defines the strategy and specific steps to identify the target audiences and communication actions. The plan will describe a wide range of diverse activities to inform as wide an audience as possible against the Key Performance Indicators to assess and monitor the success of the actions.	Section 2 Section 3 Section 4 Section 5 Section 6 Section 7 Section 8	Individual chapters contain a detailed description of the following issues: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication Strategy • Target Groups • Main Communication channels (project web site, SM channels, e-newsletter) • Internal Communication (internal mailing lists, internal repository) • The project visual identity (branding)
CORRESPONDING TASKS			
Task 11.1	Communication and Dissemination Plan (D11.1 [M6 and D11.2 M18]) This deliverable will report the dissemination and communication plan developed that defines the strategy and specific steps to identify the target audiences and communication actions.	Section 2	Section 2 describes the basic assumptions of the dissemination and communication plan, describing the basic objectives, activities and tasks to be carried out in this regard (section 2.1 - 2.3), the main stakeholders building the target group for project communication (section 2.4),

		<p>Section 3</p> <p>Section 4</p> <p>Section 5</p> <p>Section 6</p>	<p>publications and events used to promote the project (section 2.5 - 2.6) and projects thematically related to the Cristal project (section 2.8 - sister projects)</p> <p>Section 3 describes communication channels and tools</p> <p>Section 4 describes KPIs for Measuring and evaluating the effects of dissemination</p> <p>Section 5 describes Guidelines for Social Media use</p> <p>Section 6 describes obligations and requirements for communication actions</p>
Task 11.2	<p>Exploitation and Intellectual Property (IP) D11.3 (Lead: UNEW, Participants: ALICE) (M1-M36) The aim of the task is to create new knowledge and opportunities to expand market opportunities for private organisations. Best practices and recommendations will be useful for increasing efficiency of long-term partnering and further results for exploitation. CERTH will create access to Open Access/Workshops</p> <p>Another objective is to identify, qualify and protect the results generated by the consortium and to create an Intellectual Property and Exploitation Board (IPEB) and Intellectual property log (IPL) to support this process.</p>	<p>Task in progress, results will be described in further reports under WP11</p>	<p>Issues to be covered in D11.3</p>

1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The present report is divided into 5 main chapters as follows:

- Section 2 describes the basic assumptions of the dissemination and communication plan, describing:
 - ✓ the basic objectives, activities and tasks to be carried out in this regard (section 2.1 - 2.3),
 - ✓ the main stakeholders building the target group for project communication (section 2.4),
 - ✓ publications and events used to promote the project (section 2.5 - 2.6),
 - ✓ projects thematically related to the Cristal project (section 2.8 - sister projects).

- Section 3 describes communication channels and tools
- Section 4 describes KPIs for Measuring and evaluating the effects of dissemination
- Section 5 describes Guidelines for Social Media use
- Section 6 describes obligations and requirements for communication actions

2. Communication and Dissemination plan

Effective project Dissemination is an integral part of the project activities that includes the involvement of stakeholders through evaluation and specific community building tasks.

The dissemination plan is the baseline for coordination of all dissemination activities of the project partners in order to generate synergies and ensure an efficient dissemination at regional, national and international levels.

CRISTAL communication and dissemination actions aim at communicating the project's objectives and results to a wide audience by promoting the adoption of project's results and demonstrating its impact, as well as by facilitating the exchange of information and the interaction not only with other related projects and initiatives but also with activities in industry, academia, and society as a whole.

The main purpose of the dissemination plan is to provide a systematic approach for the dissemination activities planned in the project. This involves setting dissemination goals, selecting the appropriate stakeholders from the full set of stakeholders defined in section 2.4 **Error! Reference source not found.**, identifying appropriate media and events at which to disseminate, and generally to provide a guideline on the overall approach to dissemination for the project partners. Keeping records about dissemination activities and assessing the effectiveness of the dissemination measures rounds off the approach.

The following sections describe the overall dissemination plan of the CRISTAL project.

2.1 Dissemination rules and guidelines

The responsibility to perform the dissemination activities envisioned in this dissemination plan lies within the whole consortium. Each member of the CRISTAL consortium is required to think about which results are valid for publication and has to take actions to find the right channels. The general policy for dissemination includes the following points:

- Each CRISTAL project member is allowed and encouraged to make proposals for results to be disseminated,
- The general idea has to be proposed to the dissemination WP leader (EUMO), the corresponding Work Package leader from the WP that has generated the result and the Project Coordinator (PC). If the material proposed for dissemination has been developed within the framework of several WPs, communication and cooperation of the leaders of these WPs in dissemination activities is necessary.
- Decision on whether the developed result will be published and on which media will be taken together (PC, D&C WP leader and WP leaders responsible for content).

- Each partner should look for synergies with other partners to encourage joint activities. All forms of dissemination of the results of project work, should take into account (and be in harmony with) the overall vision of the CRISTAL project and its main objectives.
- Consortium partners are obliged to inform the D&C leader, PC and the consortium about an interesting dissemination opportunity they know of, even when they don't have results to publish themselves, using Teams share space or and CRISTAL mailing lists.
- Project partners needs to be informed about a dissemination action preferably two months before the action takes place and have the right to object to the participation.
- The individual contributions (e.g., written papers, articles, demonstrators) need to be presented to the PC and consortium at least on a conceptual level at least one month before the submission.

2.2 The project and the dissemination objectives

The following table shows the assumed dissemination goals to be achieved, in relation to the main objectives of the CRISTAL project.

Table 2: Dissemination objectives

Project objectives	Communication objectives
Development of pathway towards 20% market share increase and 80% reliability	Ensure adequate reporting on the benefits of implementing innovative technological solutions in the project (river pilots) and their real impact on the achievement of key project objectives.
Contribute with at least a 20% increase in modal shift to the sustainability of transport systems. Identification of stakeholders such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • port managers, • inland transport managers and • scientific community to engage and include these stakeholders and the public in the target group. 	CRISTAL ensure successful information, dissemination and exploitation beyond the duration of CRISTAL.
Building on state-of-the-art solutions for surveillance and prediction of climate change effects, and identification of infrastructure points vulnerable to climate change, proposals should develop cross-modal strategies to upgrade (including physical upgrade) existing infrastructures and reduce their vulnerability, while using sustainable materials and construction techniques.	Use of platforms of stakeholders to share insights gained and link stakeholders into project (see chapter 2.5).
The strategic aim of CRISTAL is to build on the results achieved by previous and ongoing thematic projects carried out by the European Inland Waterway Transport Platform, the Strategic Research Agenda for Inland Waterways Transport and Ports of the Inland Navigation Europe (INE), and the PIANC Working groups.	The linking of these works into the CRISTAL project will be ensured by WP11 (Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation), which will develop a communication plan, as well as by the close cooperation with the CRISTAL Advisory Board to identify stakeholders and

	encourage them to be active to represent the target groups.
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2.3 Dissemination tasks and activities

Awareness

Positioning and increase of the awareness level of CRISTAL among all stakeholders through targeted communication activities on the national, international and local level- communication via Project website, Social Media Channels, general and specialized media, targeted e-mails, events, meetings and channels of network partners, stakeholders, opinion leaders and testimonials.

Acquisition

Direct address of relevant stakeholders plus animation to visit the CRISTAL website, channels and events, to register and to become a dedicated member of the CRISTAL community by using the most effective communication channels, topics, contents, arguments and offers per target group and involving them into the CRISTAL set-up/development process.

Retention & Engagement

Creation and management of an important IWT CRISTAL community involving all relevant stakeholders animating them to become active as often as possible and interact with each other intensively:

- Contribute, link, mention, recommend CRISTAL information hub.
- Promote, contribute, embed CRISTAL in own professional environment.
- Use and/or buy services, contents, features and tools.
- Participate at events, workshops and meetings regularly.

This will be achieved by providing really attractive “living lab” relevant services, contents, features, tools, programmes, offers and incentives, all necessary technical functions, an easy-to-use navigation, intelligent push-, pull- and interaction concepts as well as a very professional community management/moderation.

Key venues for publishing content about the CRISTAL project and the results developed in it:

- **Project website:** Basis of the project communication activities with relevant content, news, materials, partner engagement, links to additional cluster activities,
- **Social Media Channels:** Up to date news, community building, sharing relevant information fast and efficient using partners wide range of SM connections,
- **Events:** target-oriented events for IWT and relevant stakeholders, especially local events closely connected to the 3 pilot sites (France, Italy, Poland); we assume participation of consortium representatives in the events related to the topics of inland navigation and multimodal transport networks,

- **Magazines, journals, branch portals:** use of both local (at the level of partner countries) and European magazines and professional portals for publishing information about the project and the results worked out
- **Campaigns:** Targeted campaigns for general audience at the pilot sites.

2.4 Target Groups including Cristal stakeholders mapping

Key target groups of CRISTAL and the focal message to them are:

- **IWT infrastructure providers, river and canal authorities or organizational bodies:** They want to ensure that they can sell the use of their infrastructure, throughout the year. It is in their interest that solutions for disruptions are developed which cause no issue or hassle to the shippers. They need to be supported with easy-to-implement solutions which connect their IWT with the European IWT network and improve resilience and reliability; they need to be able to offer a competitive mode of transport and to communicate it as such to shippers.
- **Shippers:** shippers need to be able to rely on the delivery of their goods (the right goods in the right place for the right price in the right quality at the right time). If they shift transport from the road to inland waterways, it is important for them to know that they can rely on this transport solution throughout the entire year, regardless of weather conditions or other disruptions. They need to be informed about the improved attractiveness of IWT.
- **Vessel Owners and skippers:** these are usually SMEs, often one-family-companies, with the skipper being the owner of the business; they depend on their vessels being operative. These vessel owners/skippers operate independently. Disruptions of the usability of inland waterways means for them that they lose their source of income.
- **Logistic providers:** organizing transport chains and often also running transport operations, they need to be made aware of the advantages and competitiveness of IWT.
- **Environmental NGOs:** whilst in favour of improving transport sustainability, they are often concerned that the advanced use of IWT results in a negative, environment impact. They therefore need to be involved in the project and become partners of the CRISTAL solution
- **Sector organisations:** National or regional representing IWT (road transport, renewable energies), unions, lobbies.

Furthermore, of high relevance is the **research and academic community**, as these prepare future solutions and future work force for IWT.

ETP-Alice, as a partner will also bring support in fostering contribution from different EU initiatives and EU projects through its activities. In this frame, TIC 4.0¹ will provide recommendations on digitalization for cargo handling operation and will strengthen CRISTAL results. Moreover, the action programme Naiades III² throughout its expert group focusing on IWT will constitute an added-value for getting expertise in the European landscape.

¹ TIC 4.0 – Terminal Industry Committee (tic40.org)

² NAIADES III action plan (europa.eu)

Beside these organizations and initiatives, ETP-Alice has already created an expert group on IWT via its thematic group 2 »Corridors, hubs and synchromodality«³ and collaborate through its liaison program with other EU projects: AIGIS, Moses, PLatina3, Renew, IW-NET. This existing community could jointly organize workshops and events to share experiences and expertise for the CRISTAL benefit. The »Joint EU smart Shipping & logistics platform«⁴ could also contribute to provide insights on CRISTAL activities which is supported by the Inland Waterway Transport platform.⁵

The key message to this community is the sharing of insights gained within CRISTAL on needs for developments, innovations made and pathways to them, and from the validated pilot results.

The following table presents a detailed characterization of the various stakeholders (target groups), i.e., those interested in the results of the CRISTAL project. Communication with those stakeholders includes information exchange, to ensure that needs and wants of the key stakeholders is integrated in the CRISTAL project. In order to achieve the desired impact communication with the main target groups will be ensured as follows:

Table 3: Target group definitions

Main Target groups	Description	Proposed activities within the CRISTAL project
IWT infrastructure providers, including organizational and regional bodies	central role of infrastructure providers in the pilots, exchange with further infrastructure providers via CRISTAL stakeholder workshops	Half-term and final conference. Ongoing exchange with and information of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Inland Waterway Transport Platform, • The Hungarian Federation of Danube Ports, • Unione Navigazione Interna Italiana (UNII) as member of the Advisory Board.
Shippers and logistics providers	ongoing engagement via the ETP platform ALICE as member of the consortium.	Exchange via CRISTAL stakeholder workshops, half-term and final conference.
Vessel Owners and skippers	ongoing engagement via the ETP platform ALICE as member of the consortium.	Exchange with European Barge Union EBU and its members via CRISTAL stakeholder workshops, half-term and final conference.

³ Corridors, Hubs and Synchromodality – ALICE Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe (etp-logistics.eu)

⁴ Joint EU Smart Shipping & Logistics Platform Meeting - inlandwaterwaytransport

⁵ IWT Homepage - inlandwaterwaytransport

Main Target groups	Description	Proposed activities within the CRISTAL project
Environmental NGOs	Inclusion of sustainability experts in CRISTAL Advisory Board	Exchange via CRISTAL stakeholder workshops, half-term and final conference;
Academia and research	To share and discuss findings of CRISTAL in ongoing form	Exchange via CRISTAL stakeholder workshops, half-term and final conference and participation in research and research related conferences, such as TRA, ETC, etc.
Sector organisations	National or regional representing IWT (road transport, renewable energies)	Exchange via CRISTAL stakeholder workshops, half-term and final conference;

Table 4 gives a brief definition of each stakeholder, discusses the reasons for identifying them as such and lists some of the most likely ways to reach them through communication measures.

Table 4: Description of stakeholder's commitment

STAKEHOLDERS	DESCRIPTION	HOW TO REACH THEM
Inland terminal operators	Expertise on multimodal operations specifically IWT – on how to operate the transshipment – on IWT needs for improvement	Commit the European Federation of Inland Ports (EFIP) who represents inland terminals and co-organize workshops to present targets and results at least
Logistics service providers – 4PLs	LSPs are in charge of shipping and are facing every day the main challenges specifically on greener modes (IWT – Rail). Inputs and needs will be fruitful for CRISTAL activities	Mapping main European LSPs and invite them by email to be part of an advisory or expert board
Shippers/ cargo owners	Shippers are necessary to be engaged in CRISTAL since they own goods and choose the final mode of shipment. They will bring insights on what is required for attracting more goods on IWW	ESC: The European Shippers' Council is a non-profit European organisation representing cargo owners i.e., freight transport interests of around 100.000 companies throughout Europe, whether manufacturers, retailers, wholesalers (import and export, intercontinental). Collectively they are referred to as 'shippers' as neutral user of transport (all modes:

		air; road, rail, waterborne). Alice could support to reach this organization and to co-organize workshops for raising shippers' awareness
Barge drivers/operators	Deep technical knowledge on it is required for improving the shift to IWW (barge equipment, ICT, information with inland terminal operators	EBU: The European Barge Union is the European association representing the majority of the inland navigation freight and passenger carrying industry on a Pan-European level. Its members are the national associations of barge owners and barge operators as well as (international) associations in the field of inland navigation and related areas. Engage EBU for raising members interests
IWT EU organizations	Organizations which gather many IWT stakeholders linking activities with the EU	IWT platform – Waterborne – Alice will support for reaching these organizations
Logistics clusters / associations	Logistics clusters represent logistics stakeholder within a territory and could act as a hub. Knowledge on needs and expectations of these stakeholders	European logistics association – Alice gathers also logistics clusters – A workshop will be ideal to present CRISTAL activities
Universities	Research and innovation perspective	

CRISTAL stakeholder mapping

Good communication is about giving the right information to the right audience at the right time and in the right format. Mapping all the stakeholders and their interest is of capital importance to achieving the project's objectives. The stakeholder mapping links target audiences with the communications objectives, as well as activities that will facilitate engagement. This detailed mapping allows for planning and design of targeted communication for each segment of the target audience from the onset of the project, and iteratively co-develop key messages.

Summarizing the above considerations, it should be concluded that we finally identify **7 specific target groups** for communications activities illustrated in figure below (Figure 1).

Table 5 describes the basic parameters of the communication process with key groups of project stakeholders.

Figure 1 CRISTAL Stakeholders mapping

Table 5: Cristal stakeholders communication

Audience »WHO«	Communication objectives (CO) »WHAT?«	Communication Key Messages (KM) »WHAT? «	Communication Channels »WHERE«
IWT Infrastructure providers, organisational and regional bodies	<p>CO1: To increase the visibility of the project and its activities,</p> <p>CO2: To showcase how CRISTAL project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices,</p> <p>CO3: To engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities,</p> <p>CO4: to raise awareness about IWT and citizen engagement/participatory approaches within regional river pilots.</p> <p>CO5: to build synergies with other EU-funded projects, networks and initiatives on IWT,</p> <p>CO6: to widely disseminate CRISTAL results beyond the regional government involved in the consortium and project community, ensuring they are available for the further uptake, also after the completion of the project.</p>	<p>KM1: Applications to measure, in real time, the actual water levels and the IWT infrastructure maintenance and resilience by using novel subsurface inspection data to plan predictive maintenance and improving their resilience implemented, tested and validated in the three pilot regions,</p> <p>KM2: Completed implementation, testing and validation of the digital twins of the three pilot regions: Poland, Italy and France.</p> <p>KM3: Roadmap for individual stakeholders (engineers, environmentalists, assets and risks managers, logistic & fleet professionals and trainers, procurement managers, organization managers, transport/logistic and land planning managers, policy makers) towards realization of flagship developments (individual organization level).</p>	<p>Project Website,</p> <p>Project SM channels,</p> <p>Dedicated public events,</p> <p>Partners channels,</p> <p>Short promotional video,</p> <p>Project public deliverables,</p> <p>Promotional Leaflet,</p> <p>Final event</p>
Shippers and logistic providers	<p>CO1: To increase the visibility of the project and its activities,</p> <p>CO2: To showcase how CRISTAL project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices,</p> <p>CO3: To engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing</p>	<p>KM1: Advance Corridor management system for better use with all involved actors.</p> <p>KM2: Regional policies, strategies and action plans should reflect the needs of all societal actors (citizens, private sector, research and education, third-sector organisations).</p> <p>KM3: Better roadmap for individual stakeholders.</p>	<p>Project Website,</p> <p>Project SM channels,</p> <p>Dedicated public events,</p> <p>Partners channels,</p> <p>Press releases,</p> <p>Local events,</p> <p>Promotional Leaflet,</p> <p>Final event</p>

Audience »WHO«	Communication objectives (CO) »WHAT?«	Communication Key Messages (KM) »WHAT? «	Communication Channels »WHERE«
	<p>valorisation of the project activities, CO4: to raise awareness about IWT and citizen engagement/participatory approaches within regional river pilots.</p>	<p>KM4: Governance, business models and finance structures, technological developments and organizational models to ensure sustainable improvements for a successful implementation of the Good Navigation Status, KM5: Exploitation of existing platform networks to facilitate the interoperability among systems and the secured data and information exchange for supporting synchro/multimodality along a corridor. KM6: Roadmap for individual pilot regions towards realization of flagship developments (pilot level).</p>	
<p>Vessel owners and skippers</p>	<p>CO1: To increase the visibility of the project and its activities, CO2: To showcase how CRISTAL project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices, CO3: To engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities,</p>	<p>KM1: Advance Corridor management system for better use with all involved actors. KM2: Regional policies, strategies and action plans should reflect the needs of all societal actors (citizens, private sector, research and education, third-sector organisations). KM3: Better roadmap for individual stakeholders. KM4: Real-time monitoring system of water levels, hydrological conditions, infrastructure maintenance and resilience level, including a River Information Services (RIS)-Layer in which the collected data will be made available to the barge and surveillance operators.</p>	<p>Project Website, Project SM channels, Dedicated public events, Partners channels, Press releases, Local events, Promotional Leaflet, Final event</p>

Audience »WHO«	Communication objectives (CO) »WHAT?«	Communication Key Messages (KM) »WHAT? «	Communication Channels »WHERE«
Environmental NGOs	CO1: To increase the visibility of the project and its activities, CO2: To showcase how CRISTAL project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices, CO3: To engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities, CO4: to raise awareness about IWT and citizen engagement/participatory approaches within regional river pilots.	KM1: Advance Corridor management system for better use with all involved actors. KM2: Regional policies, strategies and action plans should reflect the needs of all societal actors (citizens, private sector, research and education, third-sector organisations). KM3: Better roadmap for individual stakeholders.	Project Website, Project SM channels, Dedicated public events, Partners channels, Short promotional video, Project public deliverables, Promotional Leaflet, Final event
Media and general public	CO1: to increase the visibility of the project and its activities, CO2: to showcase how CRISTAL project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices, CO3: to engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities, CO4: to raise awareness about IWT and three pilot sites engagement within regional and national decision makers.	KM1: Regional policies, strategies and action plans should reflect the needs of all societal actors (citizens, private sector, research and education, IWT cluster).	Project Website, Project SM channels, Press releases; Promotional materials (leaflet, poster.) materials, Project public deliverables, Project events
Academia and research	CO1: to increase the visibility of the project and its activities, CO2: to showcase how CRISTAL project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential	KM1: Regional policies, strategies and action plans should reflect the needs of all societal actors (IWT, citizens, private sector, research and education, third-sector organisations).	Webinar; Project e-book; social media; Website; Final local events; Deliverables; Videos; Final conference

Audience »WHO«	Communication objectives (CO) »WHAT?«	Communication Key Messages (KM) »WHAT? «	Communication Channels »WHERE«
	beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices, CO3: to engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities, CO4: to raise awareness about IWT and three pilot sites engagement within regional and national decision makers. CO5: to build synergies with other EU-funded projects, networks and initiatives on IWT, CO6: to widely disseminate CRISTAL results beyond the regional government involved in the consortium and project community, ensuring they are available for the further uptake, also after the completion of the project.	KM2: Co-creation and participatory processes represent an opportunity to actively involve a wide range of stakeholders from civil society (including citizens, CSOs and NGOs) in decision-making, KM3: Concrete examples of pilot sites results and tested approaches inspire and support local and regional authorities	

List of business actors in the IWT market

In further analysis of the key groups stakeholders in the CRISTAL project, the focus was on business entities directly or indirectly involved in the processes of goods movement in synchromodal supply chains, in which IWT is deployed. Table 6 preliminarily defines the basic types of these entities. This specification will be verified and refined in subsequent stages of the project. A specific source of information on business entities involved in synchromodal transportation processes (with particular emphasis on inland waterway sections) will be WP9, i.e., the Polish pilot, which assumes practical implementation of the movement of goods using a river section.

The entities listed in the table will be potential beneficiaries of the CRISTAL project results, constituting a key target group.

Table 6: End users in the IWT transport market

Actor	Description	Proposed to be regarded as a stakeholder within the CRISTAL project
Barge operator	A company that provides barge capacity and barge transport.	X

Actor	Description	Proposed to be regarded as a stakeholder within the CRISTAL project
Consignee	The ultimate receiver of the shipper consignment	X
Consignor	The ultimate sender of a shipment.	X
Forwarder	A company that is specialised in carrying out the forwarding function on behalf of a shipper. The company can either only carry out that forwarding function or can additionally offer further logistical services and/or owns rolling road stock.	X
Intermodal operator	A company that offers the organisation of either a door-to-door or a terminal-to terminal transportation chain by using the means of intermodal transport. Intermodal operators are those actors that combine and refine the crude rail haulage capacity of individual railways, adding to it specific support services and making it into a saleable product. Their status may be railway, or railway-owned (as ICF), or largely private as the UIRR companies.	X
Logistic service provider	A company that offers logistic services like warehousing, storage, stuffing and stripping, etc., but in any way other services than just transport and forwarding.	X
Operator	Represented in the transport chain as forwarder, intermodal operator, agent or terminal operator having each of their function either to plan and/or to control each transport stage and/or load unit handling in the terminals.	X
Policy actor	Representative of a group of interests within a country community, a country or a region, influencing decisions of transport actors concerning the choice of the means of transport by policy frameworks such as fiscal and order policy measures.	
Railways	A company operating and/or owning rolling railway stock providing rail traction services.	X
Road haulier	A company operating and /or owning trucks and carrying out road transport functions concentrating on the physical movements of goods.	X
Shipper	The owner of the cargo when it is dispatched. It can be either a consignee or a consignor. A representative of the consumer demand side.	X
Shipping line/ coastal/ oversea shipping line	A company operating and /or owning vessels for sea transport.	X

Actor	Description	Proposed to be regarded as a stakeholder within the CRISTAL project
Stevedoring company	A company responsible for the storage of goods at terminals.	
Terminal operator	A party, a company or a department of a company planning and maintaining the use of means of transport, handling equipment at a transshipment point. Provision of transshipment services to parties like intermodal operators and road hauliers.	X
Transport operator	A party, a company or a department of a company, planning and maintaining the use of means of transport or equipment of a transport stage.	X
Transport organiser	A party, a company or a department organising and planning a part of a transport chain.	X

2.5 Scientific and industry publications

Dissemination of the CRISTAL project's results will include publications on the project's dedicated website or in social media channels, but also in magazines, journals, scientific papers and industry (branch) portals covering intermodal transportation and IWW subjects.

Individual project partners will identify such sources at the level of their countries. In addition, pan-European platforms will be identified to support the promotion of intermodal transport and inland shipping content.

For the moment, in the table below, are examples of journals and industry portals identified in Poland

Table 7: Magazines and industry portals to publish the results of the Cristal project - examples from PL

Magazine/ portal	Type of publication	Country
Namiary na morze i handel	Branch magazine	Poland
Logistyka	Branch magazine	Poland
Logistics manager	Branch magazine	Poland
Intermodalnews.pl	Branch website	Poland
Intermodalnews.eu	Branch website	EU
gospodarkamorska.pl	Branch website	Poland

CRISTAL will further the dissemination of knowledge through the European Research Area by attending scientific conferences. Partners shall write and submit papers for presentation (podium and posters) and, where appropriate publication in proceedings. This shall often be the basis for further 'gold' and open access publication in peer reviewed journals and/or Open Research Europe.

2.6 Scientific and industry events

Scientific and industry events (virtual or physical) are one possibility for CRISTAL to communicate about the project (in general), or to disseminate results more specifically. Such events (conferences, workshops etc) may either be organised by CRISTAL partners (standalone or, more likely, together with the IWT). Conversely, CRISTAL may be invited to attend some events, for example upon invitation from another project. This likewise represents an opportunity for communication or dissemination. CRISTAL already had its slot at the TRA2022 conference in Lisbon and we will seek an opportunity to attend the upcoming TRA2023 conference in Dublin⁶ and exhibition as well. The International Physical Internet Conference (IPIC)⁷, co-organized by Alice, will hold on June 2023 in Athens and will be the best space to disseminate on CRISTAL activities which are targeting to respond to the Physical Internet concept. This event gathers a wide community of logistics stakeholders where new innovations, findings, trends are discussed. The CRISTAL project will be definitely in a relevant event for reaching a greater target. The IPIC also provides the opportunity to submit research paper for which CRISTAL could have a chance to be selected by an international jury of experts.

After the first six months of the project, when the preliminary results and concrete plans for further work have been worked out, a full **schedule of events** will be prepared, at which representatives of the Cristal consortium are planned to participate. This schedule will include both, events with a European-wide scope, as well as local (national) events related to the topics of inland navigation and multimodal transport networks.

At this stage of the project, the following table includes selected events where dissemination of information about the Cristal project is planned.

Table 8: Selected events to promote Cristal projects

Event	Type of event/ www site	Country/place	Date
Inland Navigation Week	https://www.inlandwaterwaytransport.eu/inland-navigation-week-2023/	Belgium (Brussels)	March 2023
15th ITS European Congress	https://itseuropeancongress.com/	Lisbon Congress Centre	May 2023
Intermodal in Poland 2023	Branch intermodal conference	Poland	June 2023
Physical Internet	International scientific conference	Athens	June 2023

⁶ ETP-Alice is a member of the TRA organization

⁷ Welcome to IPIC 2023 | 9th International Physical Internet Conference | IPIC 2023 | 9th International Physical Internet Conference

Event	Type of event/ www site	Country/place	Date
International Maritime Congress	International conference	Poland	June 2023?
Intermodal in Poland North - South	Branch intermodal conference	Poland	September 2023

2.7 E-Newsletters

The CRISTAL project aims to issue one newsletter per year to raise awareness of the project and communicate its outcomes and learnings. Instead of issuing a single-project newsletter for CRISTAL, the project may instead opt to participate in a combined newsletter that may result from clustering activities with other project: **Ploto and ReNew**. The target groups will be key stakeholders at institutional and societal level. A contacts database will be built and updated. The content of each newsletter will be agreed collaboratively between the WP leaders, the Coordinator and the WP11 leader.

2.8 Related projects and relationship with other initiatives

CRISTAL will seek to build synergies with other relevant projects. Special attention will be given to the EU-funded projects under the same call, exploring potential synergies and cooperation in communication and dissemination activities, but also in other project activities such as evaluation and monitoring, to maximise impact and foster peer learning. For dissemination this means broaden awareness in all (different) stakeholder groups, reinforce each other with complementary dissemination measures like events and thus assure best use of resources (value-for- money).

The table in the **Annex I** identifies key projects touching on the topic of intelligent and synchromodal supply chains. These include both completed and ongoing projects thematically related to the CRISTAL project. Special attention has been paid to projects that received funding in the same call as the CRISTAL project:

- **Call:** HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01 Safe, Resilient Transport and Smart Mobility services for passengers and goods
- **Topic:** HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01-09 Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways

In this area, Cristal has 2 sister projects: **Ploto and ReNew** (described at the end of table in Annex I).

3. Communication channels and tools

The C&D channels are selected to convey the key messages and outcomes of the CRISTAL project to the largest possible number of stakeholders and target group members. The D&C plan will work through both information pull and information push and will include various tools designed to reach different kinds of target groups.

Table below shows which communication channel/media could be most appropriate for reaching the identified stakeholders. This is an indicative analysis at an early stage of the project and serves to visualize the possibilities. Of course, channels will be selected as appropriate for the target group and the message.

Table 9: Proposed Stakeholders and the communication channels

Stakeholder / Channel	Public deliverables	e-Newsletter	Website	Social media channels	Presentations, workshops	Press release	Publications in scientific journals, science papers	Networking
Relevant technology, IWT infrastructure, logistics		YES	YES	YES	YES	YES		
Academia	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES			
Associations	YES	YES	YES		YES			YES
Others		YES			YES	YES	YES	

3.1 Visual identity

The project visual identity is the heart of establishing a coherent and consistent image of the project.

The CRISTAL communication toolkit consists of:

- CRISTAL Brand guidelines
- Logotype (in various formats)
- Typography
- Templates
- Social Media Channels

3.2 CRISTAL Logotype

"The medium is the message" is a phrase coined by Marshall McLuhan meaning that the form of a medium embeds itself in the message, creating a symbiotic relation by which the medium influences how the message is perceived. The project logo has been designed and developed to support project and give a visual identity of the project processes to conveying its core processes.

The CRISTAL project logo is the combination logo that combines two elements that forms unity of land and waters in harmony.

Figure 2 CRISTAL logotype – basic version

The logo can be represented on white or transparent background, depending on the usage of the application. Three types of the logotype were designed, to suit different purposes us the logotype use.

The Three Types

<p>Third type - Logo only</p> <p>Variation of the logo using only the logotype, without the title and without the description of the project. Colour schemes and typography remains the same.</p>		
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Figure 3 CRISTAL logotype – different variants

For each of the type of logo, three different colour variations were created, with colour logo being used the most (Figure 4).

The Three Colour variations

Figure 4 CRISTAL logotype – different colors variations

The detailed usage of the logo had been prepared in separate document CRISTAL Brand Guidelines and it is available publicly on the CRISTAL website:

http://www.cristal-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/Guidelines/CRISTAL_Brand_Guidelines.pdf

Brand guidelines also include proper and improper use of the project logotype (Figure 5).

Figure 5 CRISTAL logotype – misuse

3.3 Project Typography

Correct typography is important for project dissemination activities (leaflets, posters, brochures, website). “Baskerville” fonts are used for titles and subtitles, and Lato fonts are used for the body fonts. Press release, described in paragraph 3.4 includes the project typography (Figure 6).

MAIN FONT

For Headers

Typography is important for any dissemination materials. Baskerville fonts are used for titles and Heading of the CRISTAL website and other promotional materials.

Baskerville

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg
Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn
Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu
Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0

ALTERNATIVE

For Body font

Lato fonts are used for all the main text of the website and the main text in brochures, posters and other dissemination materials.

Lato hairline
Lato
Lato bold

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg
Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn
Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu
Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0

Figure 6 CRISTAL typography

3.4 Document templates

To strengthen the CRISTAL project image and support effective communication, a set of templates for the main project documents has been developed, such as in a figures below (template for document and presentation).

Figure 7 CRISTAL document template

Figure 8 CRISTAL presentation template

3.5 Press release

After the Kick of Meeting in Sopot Poland on 11-12 October 2023, initial Press release has been designed and created to inform the general public and stakeholders about the CRISTAL project. Press release is available on the project website:

http://www.cristal-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/CRISTAL-Press-release_Nov_2022.pdf

Figure 9 CRISTAL RISTAL press release with typography

3.6 CRISTAL project website

<http://www.cristal-project.eu/>

The project domain name (cristal-project.eu) was registered in September and the website (<http://www.cristal-project.eu/>), was set in November 2022. The CRISTAL website serves as the first point of contact with the project for a wide audience, presenting its scope, activities and progress. At the same time, it represents the main communication and dissemination channel (together with SM channels) ensuring the visibility and outreach, regularly updating the audience on activities within the project but also relevant news, documents and activities related to the topics relevant to project goals. The website is already publicly launched, as its official launch date is in M6. Continuous work on the website will be performed throughout the whole duration of the project and beyond, incorporating new or updated sections and content as soon as they become available.

WEBSITE STRUCTURE

The website structure of the project website should reflect the needs of the project, all work packages and partners while ensuring clear and intuitive navigation. To ensure the provision of information in a consistent and clear manner, all partners have been invited to share their needs and vision on the structure of the website.

Design of the website is based on the following characteristics (technical and content based) and features:

- Modern design, user friendly interface
- One site, clear architecture
- Open to public (except Private Area or consortium members only section). It is an area where the Project coordinator manages the documents and events and that acts as a documents' repository.
- Responsive - The website platform suits different devices such as mobile, tablet and desktop versions.
- SEO-optimisation of pages and Web Analytics are incorporated into website.
- Pilot sites – Website has area where will be tools and information about the project pilot sites
- Social Media incorporation - The website is linked and ready to share information with project Social Media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter and a YouTube channel).
- Partners section with their logotype and connection to their corporate websites.
- Option for users to subscribe to an electronic newsletter and to access and download previous newsletter and all other publicly available materials.
- News and events of up-to-date topics.
- GDPR compliant, including all GDPR-related features (privacy consent for all forms, consent for cookies on a first visit, etc.)

The website map structure is as follows⁸:

- Home/Main Page - As “one page” structure
- Private Area – Consortium members only access to repository
- Project Introduction
- Project Objectives
- News & Events
- Partners information
- Newsletter
- Social Media posts
- Contact Form
- About project
 - Objectives and ambition
 - Facts and figures
- Pilot sites
 - Key Objective
 - France pilot site
 - Italy pilot site
 - Poland pilot site
- Project materials
 - CRISTAL project logo (all 3 variants)
 - Press release (PDF)
 - CRISTAL Brand Guidelines (PDF)
- Links to project SM channels (LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube)

⁸ Provisional structure. CRISTAL Website is being continuously updated

Figure 10 CRISTAL public website

3.7 CRISTAL repository – shared space

In order to enable day to day communication between consortium partners and to store all the relevant data in one single place, a CRISTAL repository has been created, hosted and operated by project coordinators – L-PIT. Access to the repository is also available through project website (button Private Area) and it's restricted to project members.

Repository is based on the Microsoft Teams platform and it's restricted to invited users (members of the consortium), coordinated by L-PIT. Repository has windows file's structure and users have access to create, access and write files simultaneously.

As repository bases on Microsoft solution, it also features chat options, where project members can discuss open topics.

Online WP Meetings: Project repository enables audio/video meeting with project members using MS teams solutions. Recordings of the meetings can be saved on shared space – repository, which is accessible to all members.

Figure 11 CRISTAL repository shared place structure

3.8 Project mailing lists

Project mailing list has been created to support daily communication and coordination for project partners. Here are listed all partners that are working on CRISTAL project. Up to date version of the “main” project mailing list is available on the project repository. Mailing list is change dynamically, according to any changes at every project member.

3.9 Interactive presentation tool - Mentimeter

At the Kick of Meeting (KoM) in Sopot Poland, an interactive presentation tool was used (Mentimeter) to monitor consortium partner involvement and present their ideas to gather immediate response. As it is an online, we could simultaneously gather responses from partners who attended the KoM physically and the others who joined the meeting online.

Figure 12 CRISTAL project interactive presentation tool

4. Measuring and evaluating – KPIs

The purpose of the KPIs in CRISTAL project is to provide a sense of the effectiveness and reach of the project’s communication activities. The reach and impact of the CRISTAL dissemination activities will be assessed qualitatively and quantitatively and closely monitored and evaluated using participation statistics, search metrics and other established indicators of media use. This will help to revisit the overall objectives of the project.

All partners are required to send information on all communication, dissemination publications and events to RWTH with the information listed below in addition to the brief details provided for the event listing.

Chapter 4.1 gives a non-exhaustive set of KPIs that CRISTAL will employ to quantify and describe its communication measures.

Communication measures and KPIs are tracked internally in WP11.

All partners are required to send information on all communication, dissemination, publications and events on Project Shared space in Dedicated folder of Dissemination with the information listed below in addition to the brief details provided for the event.

Table 10: Information for reporting publication

Information for Reporting Publications	Description
Partner	Name of the partner
Publication magazine, journal...	Name and the page of the publication
Date	DD/MM/YY
Task	Which communications activity does this publication belong to

Description	Type of publication / published where / title of article
Estimated Reach	Number of people the activity has reached (e.g., circulation of newspaper)
Target Audience	Describe the type of audience this activity has reached
Results	Did you receive any responses? Was the story picked up somewhere else?
Link	If the publication/article is online, please provide a link.

Table 11: Information for dissemination events

Information for dissemination event	Description
Date	DD/MM/YY
Event title	Name of the event
Location	City, Country
No. of audience	No. of audience (total if event is multiple days)
Main purpose	Write a short summary of the event
Target and type of the Audience	Which audience you targeted with this event
Project partner involvement	Which project partners attended the event
Event URL Link	Web address

All activities need to be measured and evaluated. The evaluation of qualitative and quantitative performance data gives insights that are needed to:

- Optimise the Plan and ongoing activities;
- Improve activities and products;
- Correct and fine-tune planning;
- Make targeting more effective and therefore increase reach;
- Improve efficiency and minimise costs.
- Metrics and dimensions from offline tactics (e.g. the number of Workshops/Conference attendees) and their online equivalents (e.g. shared content on social media, number of followers, etc.) will be compared and correlated. This involves the processing and analysis of KPIs from all related communication activities and therefore from various systems, platforms and measurement methods.

4.1 Dissemination and communication Key Performance Indicators - KPIs

The following table (Table 12) shows a quantitative overview of the dissemination and communication Key Performance Indicators that the project will set.

The table gives preliminary estimated values, they will be updated if the project progresses.

Table 12: Dissemination and Communication Key Performance indicators

Tool/Channel	Expected impact	Related KPIs	Predetermined target [M36]
Communication materials (logo, templates, posters...)	Proposed to reach broader audience in each category	No. of stakeholders, reached by the CRISTAL project (brochures, e-flyers,...)	> 500
Project website	Main project media for communication, information sharing, awareness of the projects, news, results.	No. of visits	1000
		No. of page views	2000
		Average site visit [min]	1.5
Social Media channel (LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube)	Increasing visibility of CRISTAL project to Stakeholders, sharing social network influence, build a web of connections with partners sharing the information on SM channels	No. of posts.	80
		No. of followers	100
		No. of interactions	400
Stakeholder engagement	No. of CRISTAL stakeholders involved in local pilot site activities	No. of stakeholders	20
Citizen outreach	No. of citizens involved in local activities, counted the dissemination materials distributed during CRISTAL	No. of citizens engaged at pilot sites	100

	participation to external events/workshops/exhibitions		
Project news	Communication of the main project news on website	No. of news/blog posts	10/year
e-Newsletter	Information for general public	No. of e-newsletters issued	4
Brand guidelines	Information about the project visual identity	No. of guidelines downloaded	50
General media	No. of flyers, brochures, press releases	No. of media posts	3
Events/Workshops	No. of presentations/active participations at third party events	No. of presentations	10
Final event/conference	Increasing exploitation and market uptake of the project	No. of participants	100

The above targets might need to be adapted according to the results of the internal evaluations of the Plan.

Data will be collected from the following sources:

- Media monitoring
- Web analytics tools
- Social media analytics tools
- Post-event feedback forms

Indicators of success will inform the progress towards achieving project objectives. The proposed KPIs below are guided by the European Commission (2015a) H2020 Programme indicators and aim to capture the achievements in communicating the project. The above targets might need to be adapted according to the results of the internal evaluations of the Plan.

Inputs derived from the monitoring on the implementation of the Plan will feed into the project periodic reporting, scheduled for Months 18 and 36. The reporting and project reviews will assess project achievements compared to project plans and the Grant Agreement, and explain and justify any deviations from the plan. Linking to the findings of the interim reviews above, this deliverable will be subject to an update in month 18 to integrate any findings highlighted in the project interim reviews.

Further modifications to the Strategy might be carried out to address urgent issues, as appropriate, in response to feedback gathered from the EC, the partners, and key stakeholders.

4.2 Contingency Plan

The contingency plan is implemented and monitored by the communications team, in close relation with the lead coordinator. It feeds the project's reporting duties when it comes to communication and dissemination and ensures that proper and immediate follow-up steps are taken to mitigate or solve any issues that may arise.

Table 13: Potential communication and dissemination risks and mitigation table

Risk for the implementation	Level of risk	Risk-mitigation measure
There will be a gap between communication/dissemination and the rest of the technical activities. Project partners are too focussed on their WP activities to get involved in C&D and tend to downplay obligations related to communication and dissemination activities	Medium	Each partner has to nominate a contact person in charge of communications for their organisation. A core communication team are set to coordinate communication efforts.
Project results are so (too) complex to be communicated/disseminated. Partners tend to focus on their own objectives and deliverables and are not trained to identify effective messages and key notes to be communicated	Medium	The C&D leader and Project coordinator will interact with partners to identify the main messages. They will be encouraged to use the Shared space and provided templates even more efficiently. All results must be made with C&D partners.
Project fail to meet the target KPI values (no. of posts, conferences, events, social media engagement, etc)	Low	In case of underperformance, C&D plan will be corrected accordingly and additional measures will be set to identify new indicator plans.
Lack of consistency of communication products	Low	Additional Project guidelines and quality control will be set. The number of C&D meetings will be increased.

5. Guidelines for Social Media use

This section is intended to be an initial set of guidelines to be followed during the CRISTAL project. Social media channels (SM) are operated by project partner EUMO, also responsible for the project website, with a corelation of Project coordinator.

7.1 Social media channels

CRISTAL Project is using the following SM media channels (see Table 14).

Table 14: Project Social Media channels

Name	Web URL Address	Hashtags (#, @)
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cristal-project/	#cristalproject
Twitter	https://twitter.com/ProjectCRISTAL	@ProjectCRISTAL
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@CRISTAL-project	@CRISTAL-project

7.2 Type of Social media content

Table below is showing types of media content for each of CRISTAL SM channels:

Table 15: Project media content type

Channel	Description
LinkedIn	Key focussed messages, with photos and/or short video clips, even technical. With keywords and hashtags (#) is important to promote the channel.
Twitter	Short engaging text (up to 280 characters, preferably 160-200 characters) content with an impactful image or video, use of impactful emojis. It's very important to give focus on keywords and hashtags.
YouTube	Short videos showing achievements, results or project meetings.

7.3 Key performance indicator

CRISTAL D&C team is planning to perform the following actions:

- **LinkedIn** : Intend to post at least 1 post/month and gather 150 contacts in M36
- **Twitter**: Intend to post 1 post/month and gain 100 followers
- **YouTube**: We plan to post 1 short video with project achievements quarterly.
- **CRISTAL website**: We plan to post 2 news/month

6. Obligations and requirements for communication actions

8.1 Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant (no. 101069838) must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

Figure 13 European flag and emblem

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8.2 Quality of the information - disclaimer

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information.

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And the acknowledgement of funding:

For communication activities:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement no. 101069838 — CRISTAL”.

7. Conclusions

In order to successfully accomplish the main objectives of this Dissemination and Communication Plan, we will need a fully committed partners to promote a consistent project identity with a strong mission, supported by a useful set of tools, fed with professional and attractive content messages.

The successful communication and dissemination of the project highly depends on the content, therefore EUMO, together with Project Coordinator will proactively encourage all partners to contribute and share information about the CRISTAL project.

This document will be updated regularly during the project and an updated version of the CRISTAL Dissemination and communication plan will be delivered on M18. We will also further detail the project’s webpage, stationary and other dissemination and communication tools.

8. References

[1] European Commission. GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER — 101069838 — CRISTAL. Innovation action. 2022.

9. Appendices

Annex I Relevant projects linked to CRISTAL

Name of project	Short description	REVISED Relevance for CRISTAL project
COMBINE (Strengthening combined transport in the Baltic Sea Region), Interreg BSR 2019 - 2021	An Interreg Baltic Sea Region project focused on the strengthening of combined transport in the region by developing strategies to enhance terminal operations and increase awareness of innovative solutions in last mile services. More at: www.combine-project.com	Outputs from market analyses will serve as initial data for business models development, in regard to: waterborne-rail based, EU-wide, intermodal services, use of terminals' networks as transport nodes dedicated to the modal shift options, improving the understanding of stakeholders (communication) needs for modal shift.
TRANSFORuM (Forum to implement the future orientation of the overall transport system as defined by the White Paper), 7th FP, 2012 - 2015	Development of tools and roadmaps for implementation of selected 4 White Paper EU transport policy goals (clean urban mobility, regarding shifting 30% of cargo from road to rail/waterborne transport on long distances, high-speed rail and multimodal transport information, management and payment systems). More at: www.transforum-project.eu	Based on the roadmap delivered for the modal shift of cargo from road to waterborne transport, indicated building blocks will be included in the business models' elaboration, and project experiences will serve as initial assumptions for market analysis. These will be included in the verification process for the further recommendation catalogue concerning policy measures improving IWT in EU transport network.
The EU Single Transport Area – Achievements, Current Challenges and Future Prospects, 2019 - 2020	The study performed for the European Parliament, Transport and Tourism Committee, investigates the EU single transport area. EU transport policy goals are confronted with real world sector analysis revealing policy successes and failures. Case studies and stakeholder consultation helps to	With this study, the University Gdansk team has delivered to the EC a set of recommendations for future transport policy measures. A part of them is concerning waterborne transport. During the CRISTAL project, these recommendations will

Name of project	Short description	REVISED Relevance for CRISTAL project
	identify policy gaps and barriers. Future policy needs are discussed in view of existing megatrends and emerging challenges which shape the economic reality of the sector.	be further tested and verified in order to optimize them for IWT.
EMMA Extension, 2016 - 2021	The Interreg BSR EMMA Extension Project aims to enhance inland navigation in the Baltic Sea Region by supporting digitalization in inland waterway transport (IWT) and by implementing new logistic concepts in the Baltic Sea Region.	Unique business experience in IWT service development and testing made in April 2021 gives the background for the networking construction, subcontractors search, transport chain elaboration. Based on these works, University Gdansk is possessing a comprehensive database of subcontractors acting on the Vistula and Odra rivers – main inland corridors in Poland. Planned business models will source and built directly on this database.
NOVIMAR (H2020, 2017-2021)	NOVIMAR aims to adjust inland/short-sea shipping such that it can make optimal use of the waterborne system of waterways, vessels and ports/terminals by the implementation of a Vessel Train.	As part of NOVIMAR, new business models are being developed to implement the Vessel Train in different EU corridors. These insights can serve as an input for the governance model work in WP4.
Novimove (H2020, 2020-2024)	NOVIMOVE purpose is to "condense" the logistics system by improving container load factors and by reducing waiting times in seaports, by improved river voyage planning and execution, and by facilitating smooth passages through bridges and locks.	As part of NOVIMOVE, new business models are being developed to improve IWT container logistics. The insights gained will serve as an input for the governance model work in WP4.
FRONTIER (H2020, 2021-2024)	FRONTIER aims to provide the network and integrated traffic management strategies of the future, taking into account new types and modes of transport and automated vehicles, the minimization of pollution and capacity bottlenecks, the reduction of accidents, and the need to reduce the cost of mobility for all users.	Within Frontiert a synchromodal approach is developed and tested in a case study in Flanders (Belgium). Furthermore, arbitration models are being developed. These models can serve as input for the governance model development in WP4.
Research in the field of 'Inland waterway	Innovative initiatives are numerous in the inland navigation industry but they experience difficulties to spread quickly in the industry. This research examines the	The high average age of the active Rhine fleet with its slow vessel replacement rate and the limited investment capability of the industry

Name of project	Short description	REVISED Relevance for CRISTAL project
transport innovation' (CCNR research, 2018-2018)	conditions for technological, organizational and cultural innovation in inland navigation to materialize effectively and successfully.	are often raised as main bottlenecks for fleet innovation. Going beyond common practice, this research examines the conditions for technological, organizational as well as cultural innovation in inland navigation to materialize effectively and successfully. The prerequisites for innovation processes are researched by means of in-depth-case studies including Social Cost-Benefit Analysis (SCBA) and Systems of Innovation Analysis (SIA) etc.
ERFLS - EUROPEAN RAIL FREIGHT LINE SYSTEM Dec 2015 – Nov 2018	The Project investigated successfully the feasibility of the concept of liner intermodal freight trains that make several short stops at a system of terminals along the Rhine-Alpine Corridor, where intermodal units are loaded or unloaded much in the same way as passengers get on and off intercity trains at intermediate stations.	Concept of a liner intermodal freight trains will be evaluated as alternative, innovative and sustainable of new services for rail freight transport, promoting and facilitating the shift to synchro modal rail and IWW transport. This approach will be included in the pilots where feasible.
FENIX - A European FEderated Network of Information eXchange in LogistiX Apr 2019 – Mar 2022 (Connecting Europe Facility).	FENIX will develop the first European federated architecture for data sharing serving the European logistics community of shippers, logistics service providers, mobility infrastructure providers, cities, and authorities in order to offer interoperability between any individual existing and future platforms. Within the project several ICT systems and smart services have been developed to support intermodality and data exchange among multiple actors operating in selected intermodal nodes and along TEN-T corridors.	The CEF FENIX project and AEOLIX project have set the ground for the development of the technologically-driven collaborative solutions that will be developed in the framework of CRISTAL for a more resilient and effective waterborne transport, in particular for the synchro modal corridor management system that will be developed in WP3. More specifically, 1) the synchro-modal corridor management system will be built upon the principles of the federated architecture that is tested within CEF FENIX project and will use the FENIX Connector technology which consists of three main functionalities: identity manager, broker and data exchange. The main

Name of project	Short description	REVISED Relevance for CRISTAL project
		<p>requirements and specifications of this process will be identified in Task 3.1. 2) The Toolbox for synchro-modal resource planning and cooperative operations preparation that will be developed in Task 3.3. will constitute an inventory of the digital services and tools that will be developed as part of the CRISTAL project (ETA, track and trace, emissions monitoring, weather monitoring, e-documentation e.tc.) as well as of existing tools and services that have proven their value in past EU initiatives (i.e. CEF FENIX and H2020 AEOLIX services: traffic monitoring, Cargo bundling service, On demand warehousing services) 3) The Corridor visibility and common open data platform, developed in Task 3.4., will be built upon the existing Transport and Logistics Observatory (TRL 5-6) that has been developed by CERTH and will further enhance it (advanced from TRL6 to TRL 7) with a variety of static and real time data from the real operational environment (tested corridors and inland waterway transportation) of the CRISTAL Pilot cases.</p>
<p>H2020 ARCH – <u>A</u>dvancing <u>R</u>esilience of historic areas against <u>C</u>limate-related and other <u>H</u>azards</p>	<p>ARCH will develop a standardised disaster risk management framework for assessing and improving the resilience of historic areas to climate change-related and other hazards.</p>	<p>ARCH project has developed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ad hoc climate services for providing to end-user's information about increased temperature and extreme weather events (e.g., pluvial flooding) in the short-, long- and medium-term future, ▪ software architecture for real time data collection and processing and user-friendly dashboards for the representation of KPIs on

Name of project	Short description	REVISED Relevance for CRISTAL project
		<p>vulnerabilities and risk for impacts,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Digital Twin proof of concept and guidelines for Intelligent Health Structural Monitoring and preventive maintenance of structures, <p>which will be utilized in WP2, WP5 and in the pilots.</p>
<p>CLOUD - Collaboration in Logistics Operations and Urban Distribution (2016-2018)</p>	<p>CLOUD project developed a virtual Logistic Single Window (LSW) as an ecosystem with services, products & applications for all transport and supply chain stakeholders.</p>	<p>The CRISTAL project will build on the findings from CLOUD to facilitate modal shift by applying the platform concept and approach of “one-stop-shopping for planning & executing of all services needed to move cargo”. Expertise for development of new transport options and creation of operational environment for synchromodality will support the development of business and logistics models in Task 9.2.</p>
<p>e-Impact – e- Freight Implementation Action (2015- 2018)</p>	<p>L-ILiM coordinated one of the project business cases aiming to develop an e-Freight information system for synchromodal operations in ports. The main project objective was to establish an e-Freight pilot that enables proper ICT integration at port level and at multimodal service integration level, including the adoption of capacity publishing/sharing between inland terminals/terminal operations.</p>	<p>Outputs of e-Impact project will enable verification of potential of integration of information and communication technologies based the exchange of standardised messages between the actors of the logistics chain. It should facilitate integration at corridor level, including the adoption of changing operational conditions and capacity sharing between inland terminals/terminal operations. It will contribute to Task 9.2 enabling development of business and logistics models.</p>
<p>SENSE - Accelerating the Path Towards Physical Internet (2017-2021)</p>	<p>The project developed a roadmap and boosted the transition of logistics by building industry-wide support towards the Physical Internet and provided an excellent overview of current projects, concepts, trends, processes and technologies in transport and logistics as</p>	<p>Knowledge on the industry requirements and feasibility for Physical Internet and its application in the IWT domain. Relevant for WP3 on Corridor Management Systems.</p>

Name of project	Short description	REVISED Relevance for CRISTAL project
PLANET - Progress towards Federated Logistics Through The Integration Of TEN-T Into A Global Trade Network (2020-2023)	PLANET addresses the challenges of assessing the impact of emerging global trade corridors on the TEN-T network and ensuring effective integration of the European to the Global Network by focusing in : 1) A Geo-economics approach, modelling and specifying the dynamics of new trade routes and their impact on logistics infrastructure & operations; 2) An EU-Global network enablement through disruptive concepts and technologies (IoT, Blockchain and PI, 5G, 3D printing, autonomous vehicles /automation, hyperloop).	CRISTAL can build on the insight gained related to the use of PI and Blockchain technology for optimised synchromodal transport as well as of synchromodal dynamic management of transport corridors. Where possible, approaches of the PLANET project shall be linked to CRISTAL solutions.
AEOLIX - Architecture for European Logistics Information Exchange (H2020).	AEOLIX established a cloud-based collaborative logistics ecosystem for configuring and managing (logistics-related) information pipelines. This digital business ecosystem will create visibility across the supply chain, enabling more sustainable and efficient transport of goods across Europe.	Expertise for the development of visibility through the implementation of buoy monitoring system as well as use of EPCIS platform for the collection of standardised data of transport operations to be used in Polish pilot. Expertise in impact assessment and governance models.
BOOSTlog (H2020)	Boosting the impact of freight transport and logistics EU funded research	Out of BOOSTLOG, CRISTAL will have access to the assessment and knowledge base generated in the project that can be used: as input, as source of gathering experts and experiences from past related projects, (WP1) guidance and guidelines to improve project processes, to increase impact of dissemination and other valorisation activities (WP10 and WP11). CRISTAL results will be incorporated in the Innovation Market Place developed by BOOSTLOG.
ENTRANCE	European Matchmaking Platform and complementary off-line services designed to mobilise financial resources to accelerate the market access and scale up of “first of a kind” sustainable transport solutions, thereby	ENTRANCE will be a source of knowledge for CRISTAL in order to identify potential requirements and solutions in TRL7 +. It might provide services in the after-ENTRANCE

Name of project	Short description	REVISED Relevance for CRISTAL project
	reducing the European CO2 emissions and pollutants caused by the transport and mobility sector	project for the solutions developed within CRISTAL (TRL7 or more) to be further developed reducing time to market by finding possible investors, financial support or partners. ENTRANCE could support the exploitation phase of CRISTAL. (Task 11.2)
Transforming Transport (H2020)	The EU-funded Horizon 2020 project "Transforming Transport" develops innovative, efficiency-enhancing and sustainable transport models. 48 leading transport, logistics and information technology experts from 9 countries present research results on relevant improved data values that can be achieved in mobility and logistics in the future.	The transport models developed in the project will support the development of Corridor Management System in WP3 and Digital Twin in WP5.
PLATINA 3 (H2020) – January 2021 – July 2023	<p>The EU-funded PLATINA3 project provides for targeted coordination and support activities to promote inland waterway transport (IWT) in Europe. Starting from January 2021, the project runs for 30 months. In this period the project makes the bridge towards future research, innovation and implementation needs within IWT in Europe.</p> <p>The main objective is to provide the knowledge base for the implementation of the EU Green Deal in view of further development of the European Commissions' IWT action programme (NAIADES) towards 2030. The platform is a catalyst for awareness, stakeholder engagement and uptake of outcomes from related national and European projects and initiatives. PLATINA3 consolidates their findings, assess their impacts and gaps.</p>	This project will contribute at least to promote and to highlight CRISTAL results for promoting the shift to IWT
IW-NET (may 2020 – April 2023)	IW-NET delivers a multimodal optimisation process across the EU Transport System, increasing the modal share of IWT and supporting the EC's ambitions to reduce transport GHG emissions by two thirds by	IW-NET could provide knowledge on innovations and solutions for increasing the IWT. The project focusses also on digitalization which could be a solid ground for CRISTAL

Name of project	Short description	REVISED Relevance for CRISTAL project
	2050. Enablers for sustainable infrastructure management and innovative vessels will support an efficient and competitive IWT sector by addressing infrastructure bottlenecks, insufficient IT integration along the chain and slow adoption of technologies, such as new vessel types, alternative fuels, automation, IoT, machine learning.	
CARBODIN (start date: 01/12/2019 - end date: 28/02/2022)	CARBODIN advocated a modular tooling to manufacture a wide range of parts of varying size. In addition, the proposed process combined different production techniques, automation concepts, introduction of co-cured and co-bonded composite parts and multi-material integrated joints and inserts. Besides, predictive maintenance will be reinforced by testing intelligent sensor nodes.	During this project an enormous amount of experience on AE emission was gathered and all this knowledge along with new approaches and AE process techniques will be used for this new project.
RIS COMEX: 2016-2022	<p>The data for the information of users is made available on a European portal (https://eurisportal.eu), developed by RIS COMEX project, to the European RIS standard. EurIS presents all the waterways and traffic information of thirteen European countries on maps or in tables, with</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a real-time traffic images • information on the position of the boats according to your rights • notices to skippers • water levels, flows, free heights under bridges, moorings in real time • information on waterways, bridges, locks, berths, terminals... • opening times of locks and movable bridges • route and trip calculation • the duration of the journeys and the estimated time of arrival at destination. <p>EurIS provides easy access to all useful information for users (marine, shipowner or logistics operator) on the main European</p>	<p>CRISTAL project will use data from EURIS platform, developed by RIS COMEX project.</p> <p>The guidelines of a European comprehensive real-time monitoring system for water levels and hydrological conditions which shall be built within the CRISTAL project, could be used to upgrade the EURIS platform and the VNF monitoring system.</p>

Name of project	Short description	REVISED Relevance for CRISTAL project
	<p>waterways. You can register your boats there and follow their route, receive a message when one of the boats passes a certain point on the network and request information on other boats, trips and loads. The owner of the information manages the permissions to access it.</p>	
PLOTO	<p>https://ploto-project.eu/</p> <p>The project entitled Deployment and Assessment of Predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against Climate change and other extremes (PLOTO) aims at increasing the resilience of the Inland WaterWays (IWW) infrastructures and the connected land- infrastructures, thus ensuring reliable network availability under unfavourable conditions, such as extreme weather, accidents and other kind of hazards. The main target is to combine downscaled climate change scenarios (applied to IWW infrastructures) with simulation tools and actual data, so as to provide the relevant authorities and their operators with an integrated tool able to support more effective management of their infrastructures at strategic and operational levels.</p> <p>The PLOTO integrated platform and its tools will be validated in three case studies in Belgium, Romania and Hungary.</p>	<p>Exchange of experience on the basis of achieved results related to the practical use of inland waterways in freight transportation.</p> <p>Achieving synergy effects at the level of dissemination of project results, promoting the use of inland waterway transport.</p> <p>A project running in parallel with Cristal. Contact has been established between project representatives; fields for cooperation are being defined.</p>
ReNEW	<p>https://www.inlandwaterwaytransport.eu/renew-project/</p> <p>Resilience-centric Smart, Green, Networked EU Inland Waterways (ReNEW)</p> <p>ReNEW supporting the transition of IWT to smart, green, sustainable and climate-resilient sector. Project will build on previous</p>	<p>Exchange of experience on the basis of achieved results related to the practical use of inland waterways in freight transportation.</p> <p>Achieving synergy effects at the level of dissemination of project results,</p>

Name of project	Short description	REVISED Relevance for CRISTAL project
	<p>results, will capitalise on cooperation opportunities with ongoing projects and initiatives and will deliver:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) An interdisciplinary IWT Resilience and Sustainability decision-support framework incorporating innovative models for IWT infrastructure networking interdependencies 2) Targeted innovative infrastructure resilience and sustainability solutions building on autonomy developments and maturing green energy options; 3) A Green Resilient IWT Dataspace and generic Digital Twin providing primarily data sharing between infrastructure monitoring, RIS and traffic management and emergency systems and climate solutions; 4) Four Living Labs designed to provide exemplars from a) LLs focusing on integrated IW and hinterland infrastructure [Gent-urban, Douro-corridor, Netherlands – EU network perspectives] and a LL addressing specifically inland waterway resilience; 5) ReNEW Outreach and Upscale activities designed to maximise impact pathways. 	<p>promoting the use of inland waterway transport.</p> <p>A project running in parallel with Cristal. Contact has been established between project representatives; fields for cooperation are being defined.</p>

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